

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fLOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 6.4

MULTI-PLATFORM DIGITAL RESOURCES AND STRUCTURED LEARNING COURSES

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D6.4 Multi-Platform Digital Resources and Structured Learning Courses

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	one city and its ecosystem of actors can take to acquire the relevant skills and knowledge necessary for a successful transition.
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Abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course

Glossary

Capacity Building

The process by which individuals and organizations obtain, improve, and retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment and other resources needed to do their jobs competently or to a greater capacity.

Circular City

A circular city is a city where the circular economy principles are implemented and result in a resilient system that facilitates new kinds of social, environmental, technological, and economic activities. Examples of which can be the strengthening of competitiveness and the generation of employment.

Circular Economy

A circular economy is an alternative to a traditional linear economy (make, use, dispose) in which we keep resources in use for as long as possible, extracting the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recovering and reusing products and materials. Within REFLOW the focus of the circular economy gradually extends beyond issues related to material management and covers other aspects, such as social impact, technological aspects and the evolution of urban governance structures.

Community of Practice

A group of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly

Regenerative City

A regenerative city moves beyond sustainability, and develops a restorative, mutually beneficial relationship with the natural and social systems that sustain it. In REFLOW, the road to generative urban development will be achieved through the attention to the social, environmental, technological and economic dimensions.

Regenerative Economy

An approach in which products and services replenish their own sources of energy, water and materials in a closed-loop system.

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1. Introduction

1.1 About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualize and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project provides best practices aligning market and government needs in order to create favourable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assess their social, environmental, and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

1.2 REFLOW Vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to social, environmental and economic impact; where technology is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and support resilience of social and ecological systems; where governance is collaborative and inclusive; where knowledge is shared, and stakeholders are active and involved.

1.3 About the Deliverable

Capacity building - the process by which individuals and organisations acquire the skills, knowledge and tools to perform their job competently- is a key lever to support the transition of cities towards circularity. City representatives, businesses, NGOs, citizens, need to share a circular mindset and develop circular literacy (Zwiers ,2020) to be able to fully implement a circular economy. In order to acquire knowledge-related prerequisites that stimulate the transformative potential of CE thinking and circularity practices, the REFLOW consortium has developed throughout the project a set of educational materials targeting the various stakeholders active in CE transformation at city level.

This deliverable introduces and describes the various digital resources and educational artefacts developed in the framework of the REFLOW project, under the umbrella “REFLOW Academy”. Its purpose is to provide a set of relevant capacity building materials while reflecting as a whole on the different pathways one city and its ecosystem of actors can take to acquire the relevant skills and knowledge necessary for a successful transition.

1.4 Relation with other REFLOW Deliverables

This deliverable is directly linked to the outcomes of deliverables from WP1-4, which individually details methods, processes and outcomes to make cities more circular and regenerative from different transformative lenses (cocreation, engineering, data infrastructures, governance...).

On the one hand it translates existing external knowledge around circularity to make it available for Pilot cities when developing their respective circular action plans. On the other hand, it synthesises new knowledge developed within the project, to make it accessible to other cities and their ecosystems.

Amongst all WP6 - Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer - deliverables, this deliverable focuses on the more formal "Training and learning" pathways cities can take when willing to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to engage in a circular transition. It is a direct follow-up to deliverable d6.1 Capacity Building Framework and a complement to other WP6 deliverables (d6.2 Community of Practice, d6.3 Capacity Building Toolkit, d6.5 Collaborative Case Studies) which provide insights on additional tools and methods to upskill circular cities stakeholders.

1.5 Structure of the Report

The report is organised as follow: Chapter 2 introduces the overall approach developed by the REFLOW Academy. Subsequent chapters describe the different educational resources developed within the Academy, their objectives, methodological approach, as well as a content overview. Chapter 3 introduces the eLearning courses developed based on the outcomes of the project; Chapter 4 describes the REFLOW Podcast; Chapter 5 describes the REFLOW webinar series, Chapter 6 introduced the Masterclass series, while Chapter 6 introduces the Academic case studies developed based on Pilots local activities. In chapter 8 we synthesise the impact of the Academy, highlighting the number of users for each material. The final chapter provides a reflective section, summarising learnings and recommendations for future capacity building projects around CE.

Figure 1: Structure of the deliverable

2. The REFLOW Academy: an overview

In this chapter, we introduce the rationale behind the REFLOW Academy, its connection with other Capacity Building tools developed in the project.

Figure 2:Reflow Academy section on REFLOW website

2.1 Objectives

The purpose of the REFLOW Academy is to offer a one-stop shop to access educational materials related to the transition to circular and regenerative cities.

2.2 Overall approach

The rationale behind the Academy is that there is not one single way to learn about Circular Economy. The outcomes of a survey published at the outset of the REFLOW project highlighted that the different target groups associated with circular city transition may adopt different learning pathways based on their role and position: learning approaches may range on a spectrum from short inspiring materials (browsing through best practices, reading a short article) to lengthier and more time-consuming formal learning approaches (MOOC, physical trainings).

Therefore, the Academy training content was designed to meet this plurality, and focused on a portfolio approach, adopting on one hand traditional lengthy eLearning formats while also multiplying shorter, easy to digest, audio-visual formats in the form of podcasts, webinars, and video masterclasses.

2.3 Educational content

The REFLOW Academy is comprised off several educational artefacts introduced below:

- **eLearning Courses:** Following a massive open online course approach (MOOC), the purpose here is to offer interested stakeholders the possibility to enrol in a set of three online courses focusing on circular economy.

The first course, “**Introduction to Circular Economy,**” offers an exhaustive overview of the CE concept, from its rationale, its historical development, its positioning with other sustainability concept, its current challenges and future directions. Positioned at beginner’s level, it is a necessary introduction course to be able to navigate through circularity implementation, whether at city or business level.

The second course, “**Governing a Circular Economy in Cities,**” is targeting city stakeholders willing to grasp how CE can be concretely implemented at the city level. It highlights the benefits and challenges of transitioning to a circular city, positions circular cities within other sustainability urban concepts, and details the frameworks, principles, and practical tools available to actively engage cities in a circular transition.

The third course, “**Circular Business Models for Regenerative Cities,**” takes a business perspective on the transition to CE. It offers an introduction to business model innovation and position circular business models within the sustainable business model concept. Beyond the presentation of theoretical background associated with sustainable and circular business models, the course offers a top down and a bottom-up approach to link business model innovation with the circular city transition. The course is aimed at city representatives in charge of business support at local level as well as entrepreneurs willing to transform or create a circular business model.

- **Podcasts:** The REFLOW podcast offers an alternative to time-consuming learning approaches by offering 30-45 minutes audio learning snippets focusing on different themes relevant to circular transition at city level. External speakers (practitioners, researchers) are invited to provide insights on good practices and challenges related to circular economy in cities.
- **Webinars:** the REFLOW webinar series acts as a space to disseminate learnings from the REFLOW project, highlighting methods, process and concrete applications from the consortium experts and the pilot cities members, while engaging in conversations with external guests to reflect on the EU scalability of the solutions developed.

- **Masterclasses.** The REFLOW masterclasses offer a deep dive into one specific topic. In these half hour videos, experts provide an exhaustive lesson on the topics covered. Two masterclasses were produced during the project. The first one focuses on Biomaterials and was produced by Materials expert Materiom. The second one focuses on Circular Business Models and was produced by business models expert Ecovala.
- **Educational Case studies:** Upskilling the various stakeholders of EU cities willing to go circular is one key objective of the REFLOW Academy. However, students also need to be equipped with future-fit skills. The introduction of circular economy concepts should therefore also target existing curriculum at university level. However, there is currently a lack of training materials for teachers to provide insights to students on how to concretely apply circularity in the urban context. The REFLOW case studies series extracts relevant knowledge from the practices taking place at pilot level and addresses dilemmas and challenges encountered by city practitioners. This approach offers practical educational material to be used by the teaching community in several academic areas (urban studies, business studies, sustainability studies...)

2.4 The Reflow Academy, complemented by other capacity building tools

The Reflow Academy, as the online, centralized space for learning within REFLOW, is one element within a larger portfolio of capacity building tools developed in the framework of the project. The extensive capacity building tools and resources developed in the REFLOW project are described in deliverable D6.3 Capacity Building Toolkit.

3. REFLOW Academy eLearning courses

3.1 Objectives

The REFLOW Academy eLearning courses were developed to be easily digestible and accessible to a wide audience. Citizen engagement is essential to a Circular Economy and the knowledge of how to transition to circular practices should be available to all. The REFLOW Academy eLearning courses attempt to provide open, accessible content to anyone interested in learning about Circular Economy in its diverse dimensions.

3.2 Methodological approach

Figure 3 below describes the overall approach taken to develop the online courses. The next sections provide a description of the steps taken.

Figure 3: eLearning course development: methodological approach

3.2.1 Development of learning outcomes

Developing concrete learning outcomes for each course was essential to the initial development of course material. These were defined by the REFLOW Academy team in relation to the outcomes of the initial survey distributed among REFLOW stakeholders in the first six months of the project (for more information, read deliverable 6.1). Learning outcomes are described in the overview of each individual course.

3.2.2 Curriculum structuration

The curriculum structure for the eLearning courses was first prototyped during a brainstorming session between the designers. Based on the designers benchmarking of other eLearning courses, it was decided that each lesson should follow the same structure of:

- Learning Objectives,
- Core Content,
- Key Learnings & Reflections,
- Conversation Scenarios (where relevant), and
- Resources to Go Further.

Each course was designed to follow the structure of:

- Course Description and Lesson Overview,
- Core Content,
- Course Wrap-up, and
- Testing Your Knowledge (quiz).

By following the same structure across courses and lessons, the learner quickly becomes familiar with the structure which allows for focusing on consuming the content.

The curriculum structure was developed during the first brainstorming session and iterated upon as the courses developed.

3.2.3 Literature, and sources of materials collection

Each lesson in the REFLOW Academy courses is based on academic literature combined with grey literature from leading Circular Economy experts. This material was both provided by the REFLOW project members and sought out by the designers to fit the course content.

In addition to existing articles and reports, the courses integrate the recent work done by other REFLOW work packages. The courses not only teach the learner about aspects of the Circular Economy but also introduce them to the REFLOW Project and its contributions to circular transitions.

3.2.4 Course development: writing/editing

The initial drafting of the course texts was done collaboratively in Google Docs by the course designers. The content was drafted, reviewed, and edited multiple times for accuracy, tone, and content.

3.2.5 Visual Language development

A unique visual language was developed to enhance the content of courses. This language was used consistently throughout all courses. The graphic elements are intentionally playful and approachable, using high contrast colours for accessibility.

3.2.6 Upload of materials on learning platform

Once the content was approved, it was uploaded to the course platform. The REFLOW Academy uses LearnDash, an open-source eLearning platform developed for WordPress.

3.2.7 Iteration

After uploading all content to the online platform, the course designers did initial testing to understand any potential issues users might run into with the platform or content. Iterations based on their findings were completed and the courses approved for beta-testing.

3.2.8 Beta-testing

Beta-testing of the platform and three courses was completed during April 2022. Invitations were sent to both internal (REFLOW) and external individuals to take the course of their choice and provide feedback through a dedicated Evaluation form. 15 individual reviewers took part in the beta-testing phase.

3.2.9 Evaluation and adaptation

Based on the feedback received during the beta-testing phase, a final iteration of the three courses was completed. Results of the beta-testing and evaluation is addressed in annex 1.

3.2.10 Release and dissemination

As a final step, the learning platform was disseminated throughout the various social platforms of the project. Additionally, short introduction videos were produced to engage possible learners with the course.

3.3 Pedagogical Approach

It was important to the designers that all people would feel welcomed and encouraged by the REFLOW Academy eLearning courses. Therefore, the language is intentionally informal in tone to make the content understandable and accessible for all learner levels. Each course implements multimedia elements to suit various learning styles and to break up the course content. Illustrations are playful and feature people of all types to honour the diversity represented within the EU.

3.3.1 Features and rationale of the pedagogical approach

Self-paced approach

Each course is self-paced and there is no binding start date. This means learners can begin when they have time and access the course content when it is convenient for their schedules. Having a self-paced approach makes the content accessible for learners who might have a busy schedule or other responsibilities.

Short lesson content

Lesson length is intentionally short, allowing learners the opportunity to fit lessons in-between commitments if they desire. It also lowers the threshold for beginning, since the learner does not have to commit large blocks of time to each lesson. The content is also accessible on multiple devices, making it possible for learners to access wherever they are.

3.3.2 Specific elements within REFLOW eLearning courses

After the initial content drafting, the designers developed two novel elements which aim to enhance the learners' experience and encourage self-reflection and sharing:

Figure 4:Pause to reflect section

Pause to Reflect

Pause to Reflect asks the learner specific questions at the end of each lesson to spark their curiosity about how the lesson applies to *their* lives. This section asks them to take a few minutes of their time to sit with what they have learned and apply it to their own situation. They are encouraged to use a pen and paper for this exercise to bring tactile elements into their learning.

18% COMPLETE 8/43 Steps

Previous Topic Mark Complete Hello, Betsy!

Governing a Circular Economy in Cities

- 1. Introduction - The Circular Economy in Cities (6 Topics)
- 2. The Circular City Defined (5 Topics)
- 3. Benefits and Challenges of Circular Cities (5 Topics)
 - 3.1 Benefits of Circular Strategies for Cities
 - 3.2 Challenges for the transition to CE in cities
 - 3.3 Key Learnings and Reflections
 - 3.4 Conversation Scenarios
 - 3.5 Resources To Go Further

How to share this lesson with your Mayor

"Hello again Mayor Arkhurst! At our last town hall meeting, I brought up the concept of a Circular Economy and suggested investigating how we could make our town more circular. Thank you for inviting me back to share more about this exciting possibility! As we discussed, I have done some more research on the potential benefits and, of course, the possible challenges our city might have in transitioning to a Circular Economy.

There are so many potential benefits that I won't be able to go through them all today, but they

Figure 5: Conversation scenarios

Conversation scenarios

Conversation Scenarios were developed as a way to illustrate how to share the knowledge gained with others. Learning new things isn't easy, especially in our information heavy society. Technical learnings can especially be hard to break down into simple language to share with others. The conversation scenarios at the end of lessons are meant to spark creativity. Some are more playful, like how to share with your grandma or teenager, and others more serious, like how to share with your boss or colleague. The goal is to inspire learners to pass their knowledge on and pique others' curiosity about the Circular Economy.

3.3.3 Validation of competencies: Quiz

Upon completing each course, learners are given the opportunity to test their knowledge in a quiz. Each quiz consists of 20 multiple choice questions taken directly from the course content. Passing with 80% or above entitles the learner to a certificate of successful completion of the course.

3.3.4 Certification visual

The REFLOW Academy eLearning certificate is created using the same visual language as the courses. It includes the official logos of the project, funder, and work package leader and is signed by the Academy director and coordinator. The certificate is intended for learners to download and share via LinkedIn or

CV to show what they have learned.

Figure 6: Certificate of completion

3.4 Technical approach

3.4.1 Learning Management System: LearnDash

LearnDash is an open-source, customisable learning management system (LMS) WordPress plugin developed by e-learning experts. LearnDash was chosen as the LMS for the eLearning courses because it easily integrates with the existing REFLOW Academy website.

Features of the LMS are described here: <https://www.learndash.com/features/>

3.4.2 Hosting platform

The eLearning courses are hosted on a subdomain from circular.academy which is an existing platform owned by the REFLOW Academy designers. The platform also offers other circular knowledge resources that support circular business model innovation, described in course 3.

3.4.3 Graphic Design production

All graphic elements created for the REFLOW Academy eLearning courses were made using Affinity Designer, a vector graphics editor developed by Serif, or Canva, an online graphics editor. Most graphics are original creations made for the course, while some (see below) are adaptations of existing illustrations that were made to fit the course visual language. The main REFLOW project colours feature as the primary colours used in graphic elements with complementary colours being used for accents. Graphics are designed with accessibility in mind, using simple, high-contrast elements.

The screenshot shows a user interface for an eLearning course. At the top, it indicates '100% COMPLETE 62/62 Steps' with a green progress bar. Navigation buttons for 'Previous Topic' and 'Next Topic' are visible, along with a user greeting 'Hello, Erwan!' and a profile icon. The course title is 'Introduction to the Circular Economy'. A list of topics is shown on the left, with '1.2 Rethinking Development: Doughnut Economics' highlighted. The main content area features a 'Doughnut Economics' diagram. The diagram consists of a central globe surrounded by a green ring representing the 'SOCIAL FOUNDATION' and an outer red ring representing the 'ECOLOGICAL CEILING'. The space between the rings is divided into segments for various sectors: WATER, FOOD, HEALTH, EDUCATION, INCOME & WORK, POLICE & JUSTICE, POLITICAL VOICE, SOCIAL EQUITY, COVERED CREDIT, ENERGY, NETWORKS, AIR POLLUTION, OZONE LAYER DEPLETION, CLIMATE CHANGE, OCEAN ACIDIFICATION, and BIO-DIVERSITY LOSS. A blue arrow points from the social foundation towards the ecological ceiling, labeled 'CIRCULAR ECONOMY'. Red areas outside the ecological ceiling indicate where planetary boundaries have been overshoot. Below the diagram, a caption reads: 'Illustration of a doughnut economy based on the Kate Raworth's figure. Red indicates areas where the planetary boundaries have been overshoot. Raworth explains Doughnut Economics as a mindset developed to facilitate regenerative and distributive dynamics. It does not focus on specific policies or regulations, but rather on teaching decision-makers to'.

Figure 7: Screenshot from the Learning platform

3.5 Overview of eLearning courses

In this section we introduce the content and learning objectives of the 3 courses developed for the Academy

3.5.1 Course #1: introduction to the circular economy

3.5.1.1 COURSE OVERVIEW

The objective of the course is to provide a general overview of the concept of circular economy, from its origins to how to implement Circular Economy principles as a citizen, a business or a public authority.

- **Lesson 1** challenges you to re-think sustainable development and introduce you to alternative approaches to our current economic system.
- **Lesson 2** outlines the essential Circular Economy terms and their definitions.
- **Lesson 3** explores the rich history behind the Circular Economy and the discourses surrounding the future of the Circular Economy.
- **Lesson 4** focuses on the benefits of a Circular Economy approach while also sharing the challenges faced in implementation and practical, proven responses to those challenges.
- **Lesson 5** illustrates the mindset and skills needed for moving forward with Circular Economy transitions and how the Circular Economy interacts with megatrends.

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- **Lesson 6** explains how the European Commission has been implementing circular activities into their policies and planning.
- **Lesson 7** showcases innovative examples of Circular Economy transitions in Europe across five different sectors.
- **Lesson 8** wraps up our course and offers you a holistic overview of everything addressed in the course to help you prepare for the quiz.

Target group: Citizens, city representatives, business owners, NGOs.

Level: Beginner level.

3.5.1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE COURSE

Lesson 1: Before the Circular Economy

Learning outcomes:

- Explain our current economic model and how it has resulted in humanity living an unsustainable lifestyle.
- Explain the role the Sustainable Development Goals play in shaping a better future for all.
- Explain the core idea behind Doughnut Economics and the big picture it gives us for the future.
- Explain the basic strategy behind the Circular Economy.

Topics of the lesson:

1.1 Limits to the Linear Economy

1.2 Rethinking Development: Doughnut Economics

1.3 Rethinking Development: Sustainable Development Goals

1.4 How Do We Get There? Introducing the Circular Economy

1.5 Key Learnings & Reflections

1.6 Conversation Scenarios

1.7 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 2: The Circular Economy Defined

Learning outcomes:

- Explain the definition of the Circular Economy and its important elements including the R-Frameworks, waste hierarchy, and systems perspective.
- Explain the three principles on which the Circular Economy is based; design out waste and pollution, keep products and materials in use, and regenerate natural systems.

Topics of the lesson:

- 2.1 The Linear Economy vs. The Circular Economy Defined
- 2.2 Aiming High: Sustainable Development
- 2.3 Enabling the Circular Economy: Systems Thinking
- 2.4 The Road to the Circular Economy: Three Principles
- 2.5 Operationalizing the Circular Economy: R Frameworks
- 2.6 Visualising Circular Economy Principles: The Butterfly Diagramme
- 2.7 Key Learnings & Reflections
- 2.8 Conversation Scenarios
- 2.9 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 3: The History and Future of the Circular Economy

Learning outcomes:

- Explain the key points of six relevant schools of thought: performance economy, biomimicry, blue economy, regenerative design, cradle-to-cradle, and spaceship earth.
- Explain how the Circular Economy is built on the foundation of years of research and exploration, both in academia and practice.

Topics of the lesson:

- 3.1 Important Ideas: Related Concepts
- 3.2 History of the Circular Economy
- 3.3 Moving Forward with the Circular Economy
- 3.4 Key Learnings & Reflection
- 3.5 Discussion Scenarios
- 3.6 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 4: Why The Circular Economy?

Learning outcomes:

- Pitch the key benefits of the Circular Economy for the environment, the economy, and society to your colleagues.
- Share how anyone can contribute to a Circular Economy transition, no matter what their industry or role.
- Explain what the biggest barriers to implementing a Circular Economy are and how to cross them.

Topics of the lesson:

- 4.1 What Do We Gain? Benefits of a Circular Economy
- 4.2 What is Stopping Us? Challenges to a Circular Economy
- 4.3 Breaking the Barriers – Everyone has a Role
- 4.4 Key Learnings & Reflections
- 4.5 Conversation Scenarios
- 4.6 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 5: Circular Economy Skills

Learning outcomes:

- Understand what a Circular Economic mindset is and why a shift in mindset is important for transitions.

- Outline how the Circular Economy interacts with and connects current megatrends like digitalisation, emerging design, and smart cities.
- Explain what skills are needed to support the inclusive transition to a Circular Economy and how to cultivate those skills.

Topics of the lesson:

5.1 The Circular Mindset – What is it?

5.2 The Circular Mindset for Citizens

5.3 The Circular Mindset for Businesses

5.4 The Circular Mindset for Governments

5.5 Circular Skills – What are They and How Do We Develop Them?

5.6 Megatrends – How Does the Circular Economy Interact with Them?

5.7 Key Learnings & Reflections

5.8 Conversation Scenarios

5.9 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 6: The Circular Economy: European Framework

Learning outcomes:

- Understand how the EU is adapting its policy frameworks to transform its economy towards an inclusive, regenerative and circular economy.
- Share the specific measures being taking by the European Commission to accelerate circular transitions with your colleagues.

Topics of the lesson:

6.1 Towards a Circular Economy: a Zero Waste Programme for Europe

6.2 Closing the Loop: An EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy

6.3 Report on the Implementation of the Circular Economy Action Plan

6.4 The European Green Deal

6.5 A New Circular Economy Action Plan: Towards a Cleaner & More Competitive Europe

6.6 Key Learnings & Reflections

6.7 Conversation Scenarios

6.8 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 7: Sectoral Challenges for a Transition to a Circular Economy

Learning outcomes:

- Navigate through the challenges and priorities of several industries in the mission to become circular.
- Share with your peers what is happening in your industry to accelerate circular transitions.

Topics of the lesson:

7.1 Textiles – Challenges and Actions

7.2 Plastics – Challenges and Actions

7.3 Construction – Challenges and Actions

7.4 Food – Challenges and Actions

7.5 Energy – Challenges and Actions

7.6 Key Learnings & Reflections

7.7 Conversation Scenarios

7.8 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 8: Wrapping up

Learning outcomes:

- Get a synthesised overview of the learnings of the course

3.5.2 Course #2. Governing circular transition in cities

3.5.2.1 COURSE OVERVIEW

This course follows up on our Introduction to the Circular Economy and takes the learner through the benefits, challenges, solutions, tools, and methods for implementing the Circular Economy in your city.

A Circular Economy requires a systemic shift where all services – from water to waste to energy – are provided to citizens by making efficient use of natural resources and optimising their reuse. Economic activities are planned and carried out in a way that *closes, slows, and narrows* resource loops across value chains, and *infrastructures* are designed and built to avoid linear lock-in. Cities hold an essential position in implementing this shift: cities are at the centre of key decisions which determine economic growth, social well-being, and environmental benefits. Luckily, a multitude of city levers are already available to close loops, reduce waste, reuse resources, and restore ecosystems while also implementing long-term recovery strategies for more resilient, sustainable, and thriving societies. The key challenge is to understand *how* to successfully orchestrate this transition.

In this course, we explain why cities play a fundamental role in the transition to a circular economy, outline the benefits and challenges of taking a circular approach to city transformation, and provide learners with a framework and a set of tools to implement the transition in their own city.

- **Lesson 1** provides an overview of the current pressures influencing the sustainability of cities and explains why circularity can provide relevant answers.
- **Lesson 2** positions circular cities within the long history of green and sustainability concepts applied to the urban context.
- **Lesson 3** deep dives into the benefits and challenges of a circular city transition.
- **Lesson 4** provides an overview of the EU landscape surrounding circular cities.
- **Lesson 5** takes the learner to a circular city transition journey and details principles and levers that can support you in managing this transition.
- **Lesson 6** provides specific tools and methods that can help reaching the learner's circularity goals
- **Lesson 7** wraps up the course and offers a holistic overview of everything addressed in the course to help prepare for the quiz.

Target group: City representatives, business owners, NGOs.

Level: Intermediate/Advanced level.

3.5.2.2 STRUCTURE OF THE COURSE

Lesson 1: Introduction – The Circular Economy in Cities

Learning outcomes:

- Share an overview of the current pressures making our cities unsustainable.
- Explain the drivers and trends that are pushing cities to explore circularity.
- Understand why cities are the right “system” in which to explore circularity in practice.

Topics of the lesson:

1.1 Unsustainability of Cities

1.2 Why Implementing CE in Cities is Important?

1.3 Drivers for Change

1.4 Key Learnings and Reflections

1.5 Conversation Scenarios

1.6 Resources to go further

Lesson 2: The circular city defined

Learning outcomes:

- Get an overview of the different sustainable city “concepts” and be able to link their strategies with Circular cities.
- Define Circular cities and understand how these can be envisioned.

Topics of the lesson:

2.1 Sustainable city concepts

2.2 Defining and Envisioning the Circular City

2.3 Key Learnings and reflections

2.4 Conversation Scenarios

2.5 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 3: Benefits and challenges of a Circular City

Learning outcomes:

- List all the benefits associated with the transition to a circular city.
- Get a better understanding of the challenges associated to this transition.

Topics of the lesson:

3.1 Benefits of Circular Strategies for Cities

3.2 Challenges for the transition to CE in cities

3.3 Key Learnings and Reflections

3.4 Conversation Scenarios

3.5 Resources To Go Further

Lesson 4: the Circular City Landscape in Europe

Learning outcomes:

- Be aware of existing initiatives at EU level supporting circular cities
- Get to know EU funded projects tackling some of circular cities challenges
- Get an overview of grants and subsidies that could support your city initiatives

Topics of the lesson:

- 4.1 Public initiatives around Circular Cities
- 4.2. Private initiatives around Circular Cities
- 4.3 Other relevant Global Circular initiatives
- 4.4 EU research projects supporting circularity in cities
- 4.5 Grants and Subsidies for Circular Cities
- 4.6 Key Learnings and reflections
- 4.7 Conversation Scenarios

Lesson 5: A circular Transition Journey

Learning outcomes:

- Visually understand how a circular city transition can be managed
- Get an overview of key circular principles to guide your future initiatives
- Know which levers can be used to reach your objectives.

Topics of the lesson:

- 5.1 Navigating the transition to Circular Cities with the REFLOW Circular City Framework
- 5.2 Circular and Regenerative Principles for Cities

5.3 Circular city Levers

5.4 Key Learnings and reflections

5.5 Conversation Scenarios

5.6 Resources To Go Further

Lesson 6: Tools to support a Circular city Transition

Learning outcomes:

- Learn about existing tools to help you advance your circular transition

Topics of the lesson:

6.1 The Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit

6.2 Circle City Scan Tool

6.3 Scoreboard on the Governance of the Circular Economy

6.4 The governance of the circular economy in cities and regions: A Checklist for Action

6.5 Key Learnings and reflections

6.6 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 7: Wrapping up

Learning outcomes:

- Get a synthesised overview of the learnings of the course

3.5.3 Course #3. Circular business models innovation for regenerative cities

3.5.3.1 COURSE OVERVIEW

This REFLOW Academy course focuses on Circular Business Models in the context of circular and regenerative cities.

The 5-parts course offers an introduction to business models, defining the concept and its key elements. It introduces the concept of sustainable business models, showing the main differences and archetypes existing in this field. As Circular Business Models are a subset of sustainable business models, learners will learn how to categorise circular business models based on their value creation dynamics. The course also provides a process and a set of tools to design circular business models from a top down perspective, starting from cities needs, as well as from a bottom-up perspective, looking at how existing businesses and start-ups can create new value propositions aiming at circular impact.

- **Lesson 1** provides basic knowledge around the concept of business model.
- **Lesson 2** introduces sustainable business models and its various archetypes.
- **Lesson 3** deep dives into circular business models and its value creation mechanisms.

- **Lesson 4** introduces a process to define circular value propositions starting from city challenges.
- **Lesson 5** details a step by step process to design circular business models using a portfolio of circular design tools.

Target group: Business support organisations at city level, business owners, start-ups.

Level: Intermediate/Advanced level.

3.5.3.2 STRUCTURE OF THE COURSE

Lesson 1: What is a business model?

Learning outcomes:

- See the value in thinking in terms of business models
- Differentiate between a business model and a business plan
- Recognize examples of new business model logics.

Topics of the lesson:

1.1 Business Model What?

1.2 Business Model vs Business Plan

1.3 Why Is Business Modelling Useful?

1.4 An Infinity of Business Models

1.5 Business Model Design

1.6 Framing the Key Elements of a Business model: the Business Model Canvas

1.7 Key Learnings and Reflections

1.8 Conversation Scenarios

Lesson 2: What are sustainable business models?

Learning outcomes:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

- Understand how sustainable business models differ from traditional business models
- Navigate through different sustainable business model archetypes

Topics of the lesson:

- 2.1 Sustainable Business Models
- 2.2 Archetypes of Sustainable Business Models
- 2.3 Key Learnings and Reflections
- 2.4 Conversation Scenarios

Lesson 3: Understanding Circular Business Models

Learning outcomes:

- Differentiate between linear and circular business models
- Understand how circular business models can be classified
- Frame which principles make a business model circular

Topics of the lesson:

- 3.1 So What Are Circular Business Models Then?
- 3.2 Linear vs Circular Business Models
- 3.3 Taking a Product Lifetime Perspective
- 3.4 Circular Business Models Principles
- 3.5 Circular Business Models Categories
- 3.6 Circular Business Model Innovation
- 3.7 Key learnings and Reflections
- 3.8 Conversation Scenarios

3.9 Resources To Go Further

Lesson 4: Circular Business models in the city ecosystem

Learning outcomes:

- Understand how circular city challenges can be the starting point of circular business model innovation.
- Get a generic approach to support the generation of circular business model ideas in the context of circular cities.

Topics of the lesson:

- 4.1 Introduction – Circular Business Model Innovation needs a Multi-level Systems Perspective
- 4.2 From circular city blueprints to novel business models
- 4.3 Key Learnings and Reflections

Lesson 5: A Circular Business Model Innovation Process

Learning outcomes:

- Understand in a step-by-step approach to design circular business models.
- Access specific tools and templates to help you design a new business model.

Topics of the lesson:

- 5.1 Circular Business Model Innovation: Process Overview
- 5.2 Getting started!
- 5.3 Ideation
- 5.4 Initial design
- 5.5 Prototyping
- 5.6 Experimenting
- 5.7 Detailed design

5.8 Key Learnings and Reflections

5.9 Resources to Go Further

Lesson 6: Wrapping up

Learning outcomes:

- Get a synthesised overview of the learnings of the course

4. REFLOW Podcast

4.1 Objectives

The REFLOW podcast aim to provide insights on specific topics associated with the transition to circular cities. In each episode, external circular experts and practitioners discuss from their perspective how circularity can be implemented in cities.

4.2 Curating approach

Topics and speakers were selected to address the multiple levels of the transition to a circular city: Governance, multi-stakeholders' collaboration, business models, data and monitoring, circular jobs and skills.

Table 2 below provides an overview of the different invited speakers and the interconnections with the themes of individual project work packages.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Table 1: Podcast Content Overview

Title	Speaker	Link with work package
Podcast #1: Cristiana Parisi introducing REFLOW	Cristiana Parisi – professor, Copenhagen Business School - REFLOW coordinator	WP1 – business design and cocreation
Podcast #2: James Veenhoff and the Denim Deal	James Veenhoff, House of Denim Founder.	WP5 o- Pilots: Textile and multi-stakeholders collaboration
Podcast #3: Oriana Romano on circular cities	Oriana Romano – OECD, in charge of the circular economy in cities programme	WP4 – Governance and urban strategies
Podcast #4: Nancy Bocken on circular business models	Nancy Bocken, professor and practitioner on sustainable and circular business models	WP5 Pilots and WP7 exploitation, focus on business models
Podcast #5: Juan-Carlos Goilo on monitoring doughnut cities	Juan-Carlos Goilo, information specialist on circular economy at City of Amsterdam	WP3 circular engineering and WP2:IT infrastructures on monitoring material flows
Podcast #6: Esther Goodwin Brown on circular jobs	Esther Goodwin Brown, lead of the Circular Jobs initiative, Circle Economy	WP6 capacity building and knowledge transfer
Podcast #7: Leonora Grcheva on doughnut economics for circular transition of cities	Leonora Grcheva, Cities and Regions lead at the Doughnut Economics Action Lab	WP4 – Governance and urban strategies

4.3 Technical development

Podcasts were recorded and edited at Packhuis de Zwijger facilities in Amsterdam. Annick van Rinsum and Thomas van de Sandt were the official hosts of the programme. Dedicated Podcasts production materials were used for recording and editing the episodes.

Anchor.fm was used as the hosting platform. The free platform allows for easy upload and editing and is directly referencing episodes to the main podcasts (Apple podcasts, Spotify, etc..)

Format: Each podcast duration is between 30–45 minutes.

4.4 Dissemination

Each podcast episode was uploaded on anchor and distributed through Apple Podcasts, Spotify, Google podcasts platforms. Episodes were also uploaded on the REFLOW Academy platform among other capacity building resources. Special posts were published on Facebook, LinkedIn to advertise the episodes.

4.5 Overview of podcasts

4.5.1 Podcast #1: Cristiana Parisi introducing REFLOW

In this episode, our REFLOW host Annick van Rinsum speaks to Cristiana Parasi, Associate Professor at Copenhagen Business School and REFLOW Project Coordinator, diving into the project itself. They talk about cities as important aggregates within the global context, about the role of citizens and creative spaces, and about how to think about the circular economy from a broader perspective.

Access the podcast: <https://reflowproject.eu/reflow-academy/podcast1-cristiana-parisi-introducing-reflow/>

4.5.2 Podcast #2: James Veenhoff and the Denim Deal

In this second episode our REFLOW host Annick van Rinsum speaks with James Veenhoff, founder of House of DENIM and co-initiator of the Denim Deal, an innovative public private partnership in Amsterdam aiming at making the denim supply chain more circular.

They talk about jeans, post-consumer recycling of textiles, the role of multi-level public private partnerships to accelerate systems change, and awareness approaches to visualize how circular products make an impact! Tune in and get insights on how to adopt this multi-level approach in other sectors.

Access the podcast: <https://reflowproject.eu/reflow-academy/podcast-2-james-veenhoff-and-the-denim-deal/>

4.5.3 Podcast #3: Oriana Romano on circular cities

In this third episode, our REFLOW host Annick van Rinsum speaks with Oriana Romano, Head of Unit, Water Governance and Circular Economy at OECD. They discuss OECD's recent report "The Circular Economy in Cities and Regions", which describes the potential of the circular economy to support sustainable cities, regions and countries. Oriana highlights the importance of taking a holistic and systemic approach to transition, and discusses how governance levers covering people, policies and places can support a fair and circular transition.

Access the podcast: <https://reflowproject.eu/reflow-academy/podcast-3-oriana-romano-circular-cities/>

4.5.4 Podcast #4: Nancy Bocken on Circular Business Models

In this fourth episode, our REFLOW host Annick van Rinsum speaks with Nancy Bocken, researcher and practitioner on circular business models. They discuss the role of business model innovation in accelerating the transition to circular economy, the importance of sufficiency to slow resource loops. Nancy also brings her insights on her venture Homie, a circular business offering pay-per-use home appliances.

Access the podcast: <https://reflowproject.eu/reflow-academy/reflow-podcast-4-nancy-bocken-on-circular-business-models/>

4.5.5 Podcast #5: Juan-Carlos Goilo on monitoring doughnut cities

In this fifth episode, our REFLOW host Thomas van de Sandt, speaks with Juan-Carlos Goilo, Senior Information Specialist on Circular Economy at the city of Amsterdam. They discuss how the Doughnut Economics framework has helped the city reshaping its sustainability and circularity agenda. Juan-Carlos also introduces how material flows are being mapped and monitored in the city to display progress towards circularity.

Access the podcast: <https://reflowproject.eu/reflow-academy/reflow-podcast-5-juan-carlos-goilo-on-monitoring-doughnut-cities/>

4.5.6 Podcast #6: Esther Goodwin Brown on Circular Jobs

In this sixth episode, our REFLOW host Thomas van de Sandt speaks with Esther Goodwin Brown, Circular Jobs initiative lead at Circle Economy. They discuss the recent launch of the Circular Jobs Monitor, a tool to support local decision makers in bridging Circular Economy with job creation. Esther brings her insights on the type of jobs that enable a circular economy and the different trends we can expect in different cities. She also introduces the new skills staff will need to possess to thrive in a Circular Economy.

Access the podcast: <https://reflowproject.eu/reflow-academy/reflow-podcast-6-esther-goodwin-brown-on-circular-jobs/>

4.5.7 Podcast #7: Leonora Grcheva on doughnut economics for circular transition of cities

In this seventh episode, our REFLOW host Thomas van de Sandt speaks with Leonora Grcheva, Cities and Regions lead at the Doughnut Economics Action Lab. They discuss how to concretely use the Doughnut Economics framework into concrete transformative action at city level.

Leonora introduces the Doughnut Unrolled, a concept that takes us from the Doughnut to four 'lenses' that invite city stakeholders to look at the interplay between local aspirations and global responsibilities– both socially and ecologically – and identify possible entry-points for transformative action.

Access the podcast: <https://reflowproject.eu/reflow-academy/reflow-podcast-7-leonora-grcheva-on-doughnut-economics-for-circular-transition-of-cities/>

5. REFLOW Webinars

5.1 Objectives

The REFLOW webinars aim on one hand to disseminate the learnings from the pilot initiatives on specific topics associated with the transition to circular cities, while on the other hand create a space for reflection with the intervention of speakers external to the project.

5.2 Curating approach

Webinar format design

Each webinar followed a specific structure:

- Introduction of the project and the topic
- Keynote from one work package lead on the outcome of one key project deliverable
- Zoom in: Illustration presentation from one or two representatives of Pilots, reflecting on how the approach/method/outcome has been implemented.
- Zoom out: one external speaker is invited to provide insights on how the topic is being dealt with at EU level.
- Questions and Answers from the audience for clarification purposes.

Each webinar was held on a Wednesday during lunch hour (12-13 CET) and didn't exceed one hour.

Topic selection

Topics of the webinar were selected following the development of the pilots' actions and the delivery dates of key project deliverables.

Webinar 1: Focus on material flow analysis, as a key step for baseline assessment and prioritisation of key transition actions.

Webinar 2: Focus on tools to steer the transition, with a focus on the governance dimension of the transition.

Webinar 3: Focus on data and digitalisation as a key enabler of the transition.

The table below provides an overview of topics and speakers for each webinar:

Table 2: Webinar content overview

Webinar	Title	Topic	Keynote speaker (wp)	Pilot speaker	External speaker
Webinar 1: 10 June 2021	Urban metabolism for circular cities	Material flow analysis (wp2)	Liz Corbin – Metabolic	Ann Louise Slot – Vejle Pilot	Simon Clement – ICLEI
Webinar 2: 1 December 2021	Tools to steer the transition	Collaborative Governance (Wp4)	Valentina Frosini – P2p lab	Andrea Patrucco – Milan Pilot	Claudia Alessio – Circle Economy
Webinar 3 – 23 rd February 2022	Data-enabled circular cities	Digital solutions (Wp3)	Adam Burns – Dyne	Stefano Bocconi – Amsterdam Pilot	Stefan Sipka – European Policy Centre

5.3 Technical development

Webinars were held using Zoom video platform which allows HQ live video webinars with online chat features, Q&A for panellists to respond live to the audience enquiries, and interconnection with live streaming platforms (Youtube, Facebook, etc..).

5.4 Dissemination

Webinars were advertised through the different communication channels of the project (REFLOW website, newsletter, LinkedIn, Facebook).

Each webinar was later on uploaded to the REFLOW Youtube channel to allow for additional viewings. One week following each webinar, a blog post was published summarizing the key takeaways from each session. The content and takeaways are summarized in the next section.

5.5 Overview of webinars

In this section we provide a summary of the content discussed during each webinar.

5.5.1 Reflow webinar #1: urban metabolism for circular cities

Urban metabolism is part of the strategic toolkit for developing circular and regenerative cities. It describes and quantifies the main flows (e.g., materials and energy) that enter in a city, which are used or stored, and then that leave that city, thus offering an integrated and holistic viewpoint of all the city's activities, of its levels of resource productivity and urban systems' efficiency and sustainability. How can we make the best use of this approach to accelerate the transition to regenerative cities?

In REFLOW first webinar, **Urban metabolism for circular cities**, experts and practitioners from the project reflected on urban metabolism, highlighted its benefits and challenges, and discussed how to scale up the potential of this tool to European cities. The video recording and main take-aways are summarized below.

Material Flow Analysis: a key leverage point in transitioning European cities to a regenerative and circular state.

Elizabeth Corbin, research director of [Metabolic Institute](#) (NL), introduced the 'urban metabolism' approach, a powerful tool for urban transformation. By treating the city like a living organism, the approach allows to visualize what resources a city consumes alongside the waste that's generated. This

provides a holistic view of the city – how natural systems, economic sectors, and human activities interact, and where the biggest impacts, inefficiencies and opportunities are.

Within REFLOW, Metabolic has used this approach to map how each REFLOW city currently functions, which local actors are influencing key nodes, and where the associated direct and indirect impacts are being felt. Importantly, it hasn't been positioned as a technical method developed and delivered by external experts alone. Instead, it's been an act of collective intelligence building. For each city, the analysis was done through close collaboration with a local driving group to ensure smooth integration with the city's existing systems change approach. The results are now used periodically refine the goals, action roadmaps, and monitoring systems of each city, taking an agile approach to urban system redesign.

As an illustration, the [Vejle pilot](#) has set out to gain insights into urban plastic consumption and to increase the circularity of the city's plastic value chains – with a particular focus on public housing, food retail, and healthcare. In the Danish city, Metabolic mapped the volume and composition of plastic imported into the city, how it's consumed by local industrial sectors, key actors, and households within the city as well as by the city itself, and lastly how this stock is collected and managed at the end-of-life. The lifecycle impacts associated to the plastic consumed within Vejle was identified. In parallel to this, the city mapped the plastic value chains of specific local sites. This analysis worked in tandem to the city's own research by uncovering plastic consumption patterns and impacts of households, whole sectors, and between sectors. This helped to place site-specific studies in a broader context and prioritize specific sectoral interventions.

Figure 8: Material flow analysis for plastics in the city of Vejle (Source: Metabolic)

To tackle the identified hotspots and impacts of Vejle’s current plastic streams, the outcome of the analysis alerted Vejle to:

- Widen the scope of interventions to reduce the upstream impacts associated with Vejle’s plastic consumption.
- Focus on reducing the consumption of PVC within the local construction and healthcare sectors (the two main consumers of PVC)
- Tackle plastic packaging in Vejle through the city’s food value chain to reduce consumption and eliminate non-recyclable plastics
- Work with consumers to reduce contamination in particular with food packaging

Implementing the results of an MFA: lessons from Vejle

Ann Louise Slot, coordinator of the Reflow Pilot in Vejle, Denmark, illustrated how the urban metabolism approach was used within Vejle circular activities.

In the framework of REFLOW, the municipality of Vejle aims to reduce and recycle plastic, starting from an MFA and site-specific plastic waste and stakeholder analysis, which can inform on the right innovative ideation and prototyping with local stakeholders and the broader REFLOW experts. The project also aims to raise awareness and create a local movement towards a more circular future, by using local testing grounds to incorporate plastics into circular strategies.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

The complex circular challenge in Vejle is attacked broadly across the different city's actors, so that development and change are made very concrete and progress in the area can be highlighted throughout the city. To that end, 5 different scenarios were identified:

- **Decreasing plastic streams in healthcare** (Test site: *Sofiegården*): Prototyping on new solutions that will decrease the use of plastic in the health care sector – and scaling the solutions to a regional/national level, through partnerships, procurement policy, prototyping on waste management
- **Creating circular loops and value chain collaboration in retail** (Testsite: *REMA1000*): Prototyping on creating new circular loops for specific plastic types; scaling this to other companies through value chain partnerships and scalable loops
- **Creating better sorting systems in apartment buildings** (Testsite: *Den Gamle Gård*): Prototyping on helping the inhabitants sort their waste better and thus enhancing the plastic recycling through awareness creation and testing prototypes on waste management/sorting
- **Enhancing citizen engagement & capacity building** (Testsite: *Spinderihallerne*): Executing citizen, maker, and entrepreneur engagement and capacity building activities with FabLab workshops, talks, BioLab experiments, co-creation processes with schools, exhibitions.
- **Testing an online platform for material exchange through REFLOW OS** (Testsite: *The new Resource Center*): Online material exchange between waste-plant, SMEs (and citizens).

What are the opportunities and limitations in doing an urban metabolism? According to Ann Louise, the results of the Vejle MFA gave a holistic and comprehensive understanding of a city's current state and impact. It allowed to identify indirect impacts and cross-sector interdependencies. In terms of decision making, it modeled the pros and cons of targeted interventions and investments. On the limiting side however, doing an MFA remains a highly technical method, which cities and local actors often lack capacity to lead without a trained expert. Second, the accuracy and granularity of insights are dependent on data availability, which can be a strong issue when trying to collect relevant input. Yet, through continuous and close collaboration between partners the approach can bring strong benefits, by providing a systemic view and clearly identifying the role of local actors. The method is best used as a tool for continued exploration and scenario modeling.

Scaling up urban metabolism in European cities

Simon Clement, Senior Coordinator on Sustainable Economy and Procurement at [ICLEI Europe](#) and coordinator of City Loops, a sister project of REFLOW, provided the audience with a broader picture on how such tools and approaches are framed within the European context. Circular economy, and urban metabolism, are key ingredients of the new [European Green Deal](#), the [Circular Economy Action Plan](#) and the [EU Industrial Strategy](#) focusing on a green and digital transition.

Different EU supporting mechanisms are also being developed: the upcoming Circular Cities & Regions Initiative ([CCRI](#)) directly supporting cities and regions on the implementation of systemic circular

solutions; [Horizon Europe](#), with upcoming calls on demonstration projects for systemic circular solutions; the [European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#) which acts as a place for knowledge exchange for EU circular stakeholders. Another useful initiative for cities is the [European Circular City Declaration](#) which allows local and regional governments across Europe to communicate their commitment to supporting the transition from a linear to a circular economy in Europe, and thereby create a resource-efficient, low-carbon and socially responsible society.

Different [studies](#) have recently been published around urban metabolism in cities, but they have been performed on a small number of pioneering cities and the concept is spreading still too slowly. What should we still do to make it the norm in European cities and regions? Several challenges need to be tackled:

- **Focusing on the WHY:** There is still a strong need to understand the benefits of urban metabolism. Having some demonstration examples showing how such approach can provide key insights for decision-making is key. Documenting the process and the lessons learnt is also critical. Understanding that it is a several step process that is more about collaboration than a complex academic research is fundamental. Designing effective communication material can also help decision makers to get a better understanding of the value such studies can provide.
- **Focusing on the HOW:** Effective and accurate data collection can be a challenge. Data standardisation, data interoperability and data access should be generalised to support the development of accurate MFAs. The promotion of digital twins, the development of big data platform at city level is also important to address this issue.
- **Focusing on the WHO:** how can cities be trained and guided to perform such studies without the help of external experts? The creation of simplified tools and guidance could help. The process could also be eased through data collection automation; In depth training, workshops as well as city to city exchanges should be scaled up.

Two initiatives aim to contribute to these challenges: [CityLoops](#), which aims to offer a sector-wide urban circularity assessment methodology & data hub platform, a decision-maker online dashboard as well as video tutorials and online training courses; [Circle City Scan](#), a tool to guide users through a 4-stage process of developing a circular economy action plan, including conducting a metabolic study.

The webinar can be accessed here: https://youtu.be/enBeaM_sjAU

5.5.2 Reflow webinar #2: tools to steer the transition

CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN CITIES:

Public webinar

TOOLS TO STEER THE TRANSITION

December 1st
12PM CET

The transition to circular and regenerative cities is a long-term process that requires systemic change. And systemic change requires brand new collaborations, synergies and pooling of resources and assets across public and private sectors. Which frameworks and tools can support municipalities and their stakeholders on their circular transition journey?

In the second webinar of the REFLOW webinar series, experts and practitioners from the European REFLOW project – which aims at co-creating and testing regenerative solutions at business, governance, and citizen levels to create a resilient circular economy – presented different governance and strategic tools and their applications, in order to steer the transition to circular and regenerative cities. The video recording and main takeaways are summarized below.

The REFLOW Collaborative Governance Toolkit

Valentina Frosini from P2P Lab introduced the new REFLOW toolkit developed as part of the governance activities of the REFLOW project.

How can we frame Collaborative Governance for Circular Cities? Within REFLOW, collaborative governance can be defined as an “open-ended infrastructuring process”, that is a continuous work of providing the means for circular action, discovering and learning, within a loose steering and coordination framework that supports both present and future circular collaborations.

Figure 9: The REFLOW collaborative governance website

This infrastructuring operates at different scales and scopes and with different emphasis including a strategic dimension, focusing on creating synergies and alignment across different actors and related agendas so that resources can be made widely accessible and pooled towards collective impact; an operational dimension focusing on building operational capacities and tools in a way that allows different circular experiments and activities to exist as a highly connected, systemic process; and finally a relational dimension, focusing on building trust, distributed agency and legitimacy while developing shared value. Each emphasis can be fostered by a combination and activation of different levers in a process that is iterative – thus facilitating the emergence of innovations at micro, meso and macro levels (from material, products, business models, to societal innovation) and over time.

The [REFLOW collaborative governance Toolkit](#) is thus organised around these three dimensions and integrates the different levers that can steer the transition towards circular cities (Baseline assessment, Prototyping and Experimentation, Capacity building...). Currently, 12 specific tools have been designed (for instance the [Circular theory of change](#), the [Circular portfolio canvas](#), or the [Matrix of circular collaboration](#)). Each tool is described in terms of objectives, and a step-by-step approach describes how the tool can be used in practice. Currently downloadable as PDF files, the tools will in a second stage be integrated in the Miroverse, an online platform for visual and collaborative work. Beyond the tool collection, the platform curates relevant initiatives and stories and will in its final version collect learnings and governance models from the six Reflow pilot cities implementing the REFLOW tools and methods.

REFLOW in practice: The case of Milan and the circular transition of food markets

Next, Andrea Patrucco, project officer at the Municipality of Milan introduced the work currently implemented in the context of REFLOW.

Figure 10: Milan Circular Food strategy priority mapping

Milan, a city with a strong background in sustainable food initiatives, is focusing within REFLOW on experimenting around a new concept of circular food markets by engaging diverse stakeholders to co-produce sustainable solutions.

Municipal markets and Milan wholesale market are framed as “places to co-produce circular solutions” engaging citizens and companies by combining food flows with the experimental and entrepreneurial attitude of three Fablabs ([WeMake](#), [Open Dot](#) and [PoliFactory](#)) and other actors (local start-ups, public companies, NGOs) focusing on circular business models in the food sector.

Starting from a baseline assessment combining a material flow analysis and a list of existing circular initiatives (around agrofood materials, technologies and key stakeholders), the foody hub (fruits and vegetable markets) became a central node to design relevant interventions.

A three-step interactive process focusing on co-creation, co-design and co-production with key relevant stakeholders led to define, prototype and test different innovative solutions. As a highlight, Andrea

presented the *Foody Zero waste* concept, an automated communication system facilitating the reallocation of unwanted/surplus fruit and vegetables between market wholesalers and food bank NGOs. The objective is to reach a 100% recovery of unsold fruits and vegetables through a data-centred governance scheme.

Digital tools to support the transition to circular cities: Highlights from Circle Economy

Finally, Claudia Alessio, from Amsterdam-based foundation [Circle Economy](#), presented a set of tools the foundation is currently working with to support cities on their transition.

The [circle city scan](#) is a multi-stakeholders process of co-developing a circular economy strategy for a city or subregion, guided by data. Cities have unique identities, cultures, governance models and ambitions. The approach here focuses on bringing together the different stakeholders of the city to create co-ownership of the strategy and motivate them to act, through a four-step approach (city baseline, material flow analysis, circular strategies and circular city action planning). To accelerate and extend its impact, Circle Economy recently started developing **Ganbatte**, a digital tool that offers clear insights based on different sets of city data (material, emissions, employment...) to help municipalities set priorities according to thematic areas (food, construction, mobility, water, energy...) and implement relevant circular solutions based on an extensive collection of existing worldwide case studies. The final version of tool will be launched in May 2022 with additional features focusing on businesses and nations.

Figure 11: Ganbatte interface

Finally, reflecting from her experience working with such circular tools, Claudia highlighted several benefits. Circular tools:

- provide a very effective way to set the scene and a starting point to kick off a transition.

- can be used as an advocacy strategy to help broader understanding of the concepts of Circular Economy.
- can engage stakeholders in cities and be used to communicate across departments by highlighting progress made through different metrics and indicators.
- can help create a vision, show a journey, and remind of the end goal.

- can prevent inertia by providing examples that help stakeholders understand how to act and prioritise actions.

Access the webinar here <https://youtu.be/Ln5W-GkBcTA>

5.5.3 Reflow webinar #3: data-enabled circular cities

Pairing the **digital revolution** with the principles of **Circular Economy** (CE) has the potential to radically transform our urban landscape and its relationship to materials and finite resources. A number of digital applications (digital product passports, IoT and AI solutions) are currently emerging and reshaping how resources flow within cities. Digital technology is rapidly becoming a key enabler for unlocking the value from Circular Economy strategies. How can we harness the potential of data for public good?

In the third webinar of the REFLOW webinar series, experts and practitioners from the European REFLOW project – which aims at co-creating and testing regenerative solutions at business, governance, and citizen levels to create a resilient circular economy, presented the IT solutions developed in the project and reflected on how a digital circular economy could be scaled up at EU level to make the most of its potential. The video recording and main takeaways are summarized below.

Reflow OS: an operating system to create federated economic networks

Adam Burns from *Dyne* introduced the REFLOW OS and its technical pillars.

The **REFLOW OS** is an operating system designed to empower autonomous communities to create federated and secure economic networks to foster the creation and improve the coordination of distributed and circular value chains. It comprises three core components: The **ReflowOS Server**, which provides full lifecycle flow processing, together with state-of-the-art multi-signature cryptographic trust in a decentralised network, from embedded devices to the cloud; **WeLoop**, which is the first

standard ReflowOS client web UI application – flexibly designed in a modular framework to assist cities to develop their own custom Reflow OS interfaces; and finally, the **Open Data Dashboard**, an aggregate data visualizer to aid cities in the identification & optimization of circular practices in material and economic flows of local ecosystems. REFLOW OS is built upon four technical pillars:

- [ValueFlows](#), which provides a flexible standard ontology to describe end-to-end material and economic value exchanges and flows.
- [Zenroom](#) which enables cryptographic trust in value exchange networks, and provides verifiable claims of events and blockchain transaction processors for open transparency.
- [ActivityPub](#) which provides a decentralised federated network for autonomous, sovereign participants.
- [GraphQL](#), which combines efficient data search & manipulation with data minimisation, suitable for client user interfaces and embedded device & IoT implementations.

In a nutshell, REFLOW OS enables decentralised, **federated** networking for continuous exchange of economic and material flows amongst autonomous peers, based on a standard shared vocabulary for **tracking** and **tracing economic** and material resource flows across their full lifecycles. It offers a state-of-the-art cryptographic verification of material flows integrated with blockchain technologies for transparent trust and reliable auditing through **material passports**. Lastly, it integrates aggregate **data visualization** tools to aid in discovery & optimisation of further circular practice opportunities across material and economic flows.

Reflow os in practice

What concrete applications can REFLOW OS support? **Stefano Bocconi** from [Waaq](#) presented one specific use case, in the context of Amsterdam’s goals to make textiles value chains more circular.

Taking as a starting point the outcomes of a Material Flow Analysis highlighting the linearity of the textile flowing in and out of the dutch city, results showed that discarded textile items mainly end up incinerated together with regular waste. Developing solutions that can support an extended use of textile during its useful lifetime is thus a key priority to reduce textile waste at city level.

In that regard, the [Swapshop](#) concept store, which enables the “swapping” of used clothes between users, is a relevant initiative aligned with the city’s circularity goals. But how can we keep track of the items and get data on how these are swapped, used, and recycled? How can we get insights on the motivation of the customers to swap? Would creating a storytelling associated with each item provide additional incentive for the customers to take care of its clothes?

Figure 12: Screenshots of Swapshop Application

There, REFLOW OS became useful to model the flow of events occurring between each swap and keep track of associated relevant data. By adding a QR code to the swapped items, each item can be characterized through an innovative chatbot conversation asking each item's owner to provide easy to input information on the item. The prototype is currently in its pilot phase and will in a next phase offer the possibility to track textile items beyond the use phase, by including collectors and recyclers in the conversation.

How can data tracking support the development of waste free urban food systems? That's one key challenge the city of Milan is currently tackling in the context of REFLOW. **Enrico Bassi** from **Opendot**, an active member of the Milan REFLOW pilot, presented **Botto**, an innovative solution developed in the context of municipal food markets of the Italian city.

The reduction of food waste is one of the priorities of the Milan Food Policy and since 2016 the Municipality of Milan has worked to find solutions to reduce food waste and to innovate the ways of recovering food to be donated to the needy. Following a co-creating process involving different local stakeholders, the Botto solution was designed as an automated communication system, integrated with a signal and tracking system that facilitates the reallocation of surplus food between fruit and vegetable wholesalers, organizations fighting food waste and other organisations helping people in need.

Figure 13: Screenshot of Botto solution

The system runs via an IOT device (“Botto”) and a telegram bot, to simplify the donation process. For those on the supply side, using Botto allows for the reduced expenses on waste management and improved social and environmental sustainability. On the demand side, Botto makes it possible for actors to have a quick and real-time overview of the available food. Thus, charities do not need to spend time on coordinating the redistribution of food and the logistics involved with these activities. There, Reflow OS allows for a complete tracking of the characteristics of the surplus food donated (type, quantity, quality) making it possible to monitor the overall amount of food waste diverted.

Future directions in the digitalisation of circular economy

In the last three years, The REFLOW project has demonstrated several concrete applications on how to use data and tech to make cities more circular. But what are the next steps at EU level to scale up a digital circular economy? **Stefan Sipka** from the **European Policy Centre (EPC)** highlighted existing challenges currently hindering the development of a digital circular economy: lack of access to good quality data, concerns over data protection and security, the difficulty in managing supply chain complexities and the lack of incentives for businesses to share data. As a response, several policy recommendations should be taken forward: establish a sustainable digital information system for circularity in the EU; bridge the European data space(s) with circular economy to enable effective information transfer; establish harmonized rules on using digital product passports and use economic and financial tools to enhance digital information transfer in circular value chains.

Access the webinar here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BIMyOM5msgA>

6. REFLOW Masterclasses

6.1 Objectives

The Reflow Masterclasses offer a deep dive into dedicated topics relevant to the transition to circular cities. In a condensed 30 min lecture, experts provide an overview of key knowledge and insights on circular economy related topics.

6.2 Curating approach

The Masterclasses were produced in the last six months of the project to offer an in-depth condensed knowledge related to some specific focuses of the Reflow project: Biomaterials, and business model innovation.

Table 3: Overview of Masterclasses

Masterclass #	Title	Topic	Lecture by
Masterclass #1	Biomaterials, a key ingredient for a circular and regenerative economy	Biomaterials	Materiom
Masterclass #2	Business model innovation, a key enabler of a Circular and regenerative Economy	Business model, innovation,	Ecovala

6.3 Overview of Masterclasses

6.3.1 BioMaterials: A key ingredients to a circular and regenerative economy.

This class aims to introduce you to the world of biomaterials from a circular and regenerative perspective, emphasizing the needs, analyse and take into account multiple layers of this emerging topic.

The class was developed by Materiom. Materiom provides open-source recipes and data on materials made from abundant sources of natural ingredients, like agricultural waste. By making this knowledge open, the organisation accelerates materials development and lower barriers to entry in materials markets around the world. Materiom works with companies, cities and communities to support the development of local biomaterial supply chains that nourish local ecologies and economies.

<https://materiom.org>

The masterclass is available on the REFLOW Academy section of the REFLOW website.

6.3.2 Business model innovation: a key enabler of a circular and regenerative economy

This class aims to introduce you to the world of business model innovation, a key enabler to transition to a circular economy.

The class was developed by Ecovala.

Ecovala is a Finland based consultancy focusing on circular and regenerative economy with a focus on business model and systems innovation. Ecovala has been leading the development of the circular.academy since 2013, offering tools and canvases that can support companies and start-ups to design circular business models.

www.ecovala.eu

The masterclass is available on the REFLOW Academy section of the REFLOW website

7. REFLOW Case Studies

7.1 Objectives

The open source REFLOW case studies collection is built upon the learnings from activities and actions taking place in the pilot cities of the REFLOW project. The case studies link practice and theory and are designed to be used as teaching material in different academic settings, as circular economy transition in cities can be addressed from different academic lenses – urban studies, consumer studies, business studies, sustainability studies...

7.2 Methodological approach

The case studies are an integral part of deliverable 6.5, the methodological approach is described in the deliverable.

7.3 Dissemination

Each case studies were uploaded on the Reflow website and disseminated through the different communication channels of the project. Additional dissemination activities focused on publishing the cases in different professional groups associated to education and circular economy.

7.4 Overview of case studies

7.4.2 Reflow case study #1: vejle's road to becoming a circular plasti-city

Synopsis of the Case

This case is based on a real organisation that has carried out activities as part of the European Union Horizon 2020 project, REFLOW. The protagonists in this case are the Vejle pilot team. The team needs to choose one particular focal area, namely a specific industry with a respective micro-test site where they will develop and implement a circular intervention to close the loop on their circular plastic streams in the city. The team has four key focal areas, each targeting a specific industry (construction, food retail, healthcare, and households) which is paired with a micro-test site where the team will carry out their circular intervention. Each key focal area/test site is unique and targets certain demographics, types of plastics, and has their own challenges.

The case goes over key insights that feed into the decision-making process of the Vejle team. The ultimate goal for the Vejle team is achieve a circular plastics in the city. In order to do this, they are implementing this small experiment, but want to ensure that while this is a micro-test that it is still impactful in the long-term, can reach short-term targets, and can also be scaled in the future to help to foster further circular transitions across the city, the region, and beyond.

This is a decision-based case. It asks the students to step into the shoes of the Vejle pilot team. The case study challenges students to formulate recommendations regarding which key focal area the pilot should choose and why.

Target Group

The case is suitable for undergraduate and graduate levels in project management, strategic management, circular economy, and sustainability courses.

Learning Objectives and Key Issues

The learning objectives of the case sets out for students to evaluate circular intervention options for plastic material flows that would lead to long-lasting impact, short-term project goals, and be scalable. After completion of the case, students should be able to understand the following:

- The plastic problem in Denmark and Vejle, including understanding different plastic types, use, and characteristics
- Environmental impacts of different plastic types – both in regard to production and waste management
- Plastic use and waste management across sectors
- Circular economy as a solution
- Assessing a portfolio of projects and seeing how they fit the goals of the REFLOW Vejle pilot organisation

Teaching material

Download the [full case study](#)

Download the [teaching guide](#)

7.4.3 Reflow case study #2: wasted efforts in Amsterdam

Synopsis of the Case

This case is based on a real organisation that has carried out activities as part of the European Union Horizon 2020 project, REFLOW.

The protagonists in this case are the Amsterdam pilot team. The overall long-term goal the team seeks reach is to transition their textile stream in the city towards becoming circular and regenerative. Short-term, the pilot team focuses on empowering citizens and changing linear behaviours associated with textiles across two key aims:

1. Discarding of fewer textiles by extending their life through reuse, repair, revaluing, and reducing
2. Increasing the collection of home textile waste at the city-level by informing and engaging citizens to discard correctly

The case goes over key insights into the decision-making process of the Amsterdam team, including facts on linearity in the textile industry at the global and local level, information about the citizens of

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Amsterdam, and a list of potential activities the team needs to decide on. The Amsterdam team is faced with a timely decision where they need to pick five key activities that would allow them to reach specific project targets in the short-term and that would also induce long-lasting change in the future.

This is a decision-based case. It asks the students to step into the shoes of the Amsterdam pilot team. The case study challenges students to formulate recommendations regarding which key activities the pilot should carry out and to assess the activities that could lead to behavioural change.

Target Group

The case is suitable for graduate levels in consumer behaviour, service design and behaviour, environmental psychology, circular economy, and behavioural economics courses.

Learning Objectives and Key Issues

The learning objectives of the case sets out for students to evaluate solutions that would most likely lead to behavioural change in citizens, while also meeting project targets and goals. After completion of this case, students should be able to understand the following:

- The challenges of linear model in the textile industry and the transition to circular economy
- The circular economy in relation to the textile industry
- The gaps between good intentions and actions
- Different behavioural change strategies to influence action in citizens

Teaching material

Download the [full case study](#)

Download the [teaching guide](#)

7.4.4 Reflow case study #3: Planning a Circular Paris

Synopsis of the Case

This case is a fictionalised account of a real organisation of partners that have carried out activities as part of the European Union Horizon 2020 project, REFLOW.

The protagonist in the case is Amelie, an urban planner for the Paris region. Amelie stakes lie in the municipality's vision for urban development and growth – including a focus on ensuring that the city has affordable housing to address the socioeconomic gap growing in the city, sustainable active mobility, multifunctionality, urban economic growth, and ensuring that the Paris vision towards circular economy is upheld. She is approached by the REFLOW Paris pilot team who are interested in a site in the city that could be used as a storage facility – something that they deem as a crucial component towards transitioning the city towards the circular economy. The case introduces four personas who all each have their own stake in the site and their own take on the future direction of Paris' urban development.

The case concludes with Amelie providing her recommendations on the future development of the site.

Target Group

The case is suitable for both undergraduate and graduate students taking urban planning/urban studies, economic geography, circular economy, and strategic decision making courses.

Learning Objectives

The learning objectives of this case seek to invoke discussion into the complexities of urban planning in high-cost, growing cities where urban planning practitioners must balance a portfolio of interests while also adhering to their own stakes working towards municipal visions and objectives. After completion of the case, students will be able to:

- Discuss urban development in relation to a variety of land uses
- Discuss the interests and stakes that an urban planner must balance
- Discuss possible facilitation strategies that can be used
- Understand a portfolio of challenges and intersecting interests in a city
- Create connections between circular economy and urban planning

Teaching material

Download the [full case study](#)

Download the [teaching guide](#)

7.4.5 REFLOW Case Study #4: Is Berlin getting into hot (waste) Water?

Synopsis of the Case

This case is based on a real organisation that has carried out activities as part of the European Union Horizon 2020 project, REFLOW. The case is fictional but, inspired by real events that have occurred.

The protagonist of this case is the head of the Wastewater Heat Department at the water agency Berliner Wasserbetriebe (BWB). BWB is responsible to providing drinking water and wastewater treatment for the city of Berlin. These services and supplies are considered critical infrastructures, and any disruptions to their operations could cause a series of challenges and risks for the city and Germany as a whole. The case focuses on the dilemma of the head of the Wastewater Heat Department as they assess whether to release data on these critical infrastructures in the name of a greener and more circular and regenerative future.

The case is set 2.5 years into the 3-year timeline of the REFLOW project, centring around a solution that the Berlin pilot team has developed to harness the potential of wastewater heat as a climate-neutral source for the city through the power of data. BWB's R&D Department is a key member of the Berlin pilot team, where they have played an instrumental role in giving access to key data for the development of the solution, the Wastewater Heat Radar. As things were on the way to finalising the development of this solution, the Waste Heat Department, a department in BWB that were outside of the REFLOW project informed the Berlin pilot team that they need to put a halt to their solution. With the rising concern of critical infrastructure (in)security and the obligations for BWB to ensure that these supplies of water and wastewater services are not interrupted by threats or attacks, they needed to discuss the pros and cons of releasing this critical infrastructure data.

Students are asked to put themselves in the shoes of the head of the Wastewater Heat Department at BWB and to consider the question: should a stop be put on the release of wastewater heat potential data or risk the potential security threat to critical infrastructure in Berlin? Pros and cons are outlined in the case study including climate-neutral goals alongside the risks and vulnerabilities associated with publishing information and data on critical infrastructure.

Target Group

The case is suitable for undergraduate and graduate levels in courses on strategic decision making, the energy transition and innovation, cybersecurity, and circular economy.

Learning Objectives

- After completion of the case, students should be able to understand the following:
- The potential of wastewater heat as a climate-neutral source of energy
- The importance of data in circular transitions, specifically for wastewater heat
- The challenges of handling critical infrastructure data and how this affects innovative technological solutions
- Arguing for or against a decision

Teaching material

Download the full [case study](#)

Download the [teaching guide](#)

7.4.5 REFLOW Case Study #5: Energetic efforts in Cluj-Napoca

Synopsis of the Case

This case is based on a real organisation that has carried out activities as part of the European Union Horizon 2020 project, REFLOW. While the case is based on a real organisation and other elements, the case is fictionalised. The main protagonist is the coordinator of the Cluj-Napoca pilot city, Mihai Barbu. The coordinator and his team encounter a barrier to accessing energy consumption data needed for a technological solution which they believe could help to raise awareness on energy consumption and lead to the increased energy efficiency, reduction in energy consumption, and towards the overall energy and circular transition in the city. The gatekeepers of the data, the partly state-owned energy distributor, does not want to release their data needed for the technological solution. With the clock ticking on the REFLOW project's timespan, the coordinator must now figure out what the next steps of the Cluj-Napoca pilot will be. The students are asked to assess what could be done in this situation. Could there be any potential for making a convincing argument or should they go in a different direction, if so, what?

Target Group

The case is suitable for courses in energy transition, strategy and innovation, data governance, strategic decision making, and sustainability courses at the undergraduate and graduate levels.

Learning Objectives

The learning objectives of this case aim to have students evaluate and assess the situation with sustainable and circular projects and the barriers to data sharing. With the pressing need to transition towards more sustainable and circular economies, technological solutions play a key role in ensuring this. However, accessing data is not always easy, especially when there are challenges associated with actors and large public organisations that are more rigid and bureaucratic. After completion of this case, students should be able to understand the following:

- The barriers to data sharing for technological solutions when dealing with bureaucratic and rigid actors
- Learn about the importance of energy transitions and the reality of making sustainable and circular solutions when you do not have feasible access to the data

The case also allows students to make their own assessment of the situation and to identify pathways for how to move forward with a project when things do not go as planned. Students can also be asked to evaluate the scalability and replicability of this place-based situation and if their solution to the dilemma could be translated to other contexts.

Teaching material

Download the full [case study](#)

Download the [teaching guide](#)

7.4.6 REFLOW Case Study #6:

Synopsis of the Case

This case is based on a real organisation in Milan that has carried out activities as part of the European Union Horizon 2020 project, REFLOW.

The Milan REFLOW team, comprised of system designers, researchers, makers, and municipal actors, set out to tackle the overwhelming amounts of food waste being produced across the city of Milan. The team decided to focus on the fruit and vegetable wholesalers within Municipal market, SogeMi. In co-creation with the market, the team developed the innovative circular solution, BOTTO, that would enable the recovery of surplus fruits and vegetables.

While the REFLOW project and its funding was coming to an end, Milan's transition towards a more circular and generative urban food system has just begun. Therefore, to sustain the Milan team's solution beyond the REFLOW project, they needed to find new sources of income and new investors to further develop and ensure the solutions scalability.

The case provides key insights on the complex structure of the Milanese redistribution network for surplus food, including a short description of key actors in the network – wholesalers, re (distributors) and charities. It goes over how the Milan Team intends to assist the network with a more efficient handling of surplus food, that ultimately can be redistributed to those in need. Throughout the case, stakeholders' potential benefits from using the platform as well challenges concerning their willingness to pay for the service is briefly considered. Students are asked to put themselves in the shoes of Eva, a freelance consultant with experience in business modelling, to consult the Milan Reflow team on choosing a revenue model for the BOTTO solution. Having in mind the different needs of actors in the urban food network, Eva needs to recognize the balance between each actor's value capture and risks, and accordingly, their ability and willingness to pay for the service.

Target Group

The case is suitable for undergraduate and postgraduate levels in courses on strategic decision making, sales management, entrepreneurship, and circular economy.

Learning Objectives

After completing the case, students should be able to understand the following:

- Apply theoretical knowledge on revenue modelling to a practical business case
- Understand, reflect upon, and contrast different revenue model approaches
- Identify, design, plan and assess a revenue model for the specific case (advantages and disadvantages).

Teaching material

Download the full [case study](#)

Download the [teaching guide](#)

8. Impact of REFLOW Academy

The chapter highlights the key performance indicators associated with the REFLOW Academy.

8.1 Podcasts

According to [Feedpost](#), which ranks the best podcasts about Circular Economy from thousands of podcasts on the web ranked by traffic, social media followers, domain authority & freshness, REFLOW Podcast is ranked 4th position alongside Circular Economy Podcast, the Circular Economy Show from Ellen MacArthur Foundation and The Circular Economy Playbook.

INDICATOR	RESULTS
Number of streams	Podcast 1: 117 Podcast 2: 58 Podcast 3: 101 Podcast 4: 17 Podcast 5: 19 Podcast 6: 9

Age demographics of listeners: 37% of listeners are aged 23-27, 29% are aged 28-24. Another 26% are aged 35-59. 64% are female, 32% male, 4% unspecified.

Figure 14:Podcast Demographics

8.2 Webinars

Reflow webinars generally attracted up to 100 participants- Post webinar streaming range from 60 to 143 individual views.

INDICATOR	RESULTS
<i>Number of registrations</i>	Webinar 1: 110 Webinar 2: 69 Webinar 3: 128
<i>Number of viewers (post-webinar, Youtube)</i>	Webinar 1: 143 Webinar 2: 138 Webinar 3: 60

8.3 Masterclasses

Masterclasses were only released in the last trimester of the project.

By the time of writing this deliverable, the masterclass on biomaterials was viewed 136 times, while the last addition on business model innovation was viewed 36 times.

INDICATOR	RESULTS
<i>Number of viewers</i>	Masterclass 1: 136 Masterclass 2: 36

8.4 Ecourses

8.4.1 Betatesting

Betatesting of the online platform and its evaluation is detailed in annex 1. It provides an evaluation of the platform and details the overall satisfaction rate of the structure, content and learning objectives. The evaluation provided useful feedback for the final iterations of the platform. Overall, 100% of betasters would recommend the platform to their peers, with 25% agreeing / 75% strongly agreeing that the content meets the courses objectives.

8.4.2 Platform usage – preliminary results

The platform was officially released 1st May 22. In the first 3 weeks, we monitored 67 registrations to the platform.

INDICATOR	RESULTS
Number of registrations	Total registrations: 67 (platform opened 1 st May 22)

9 Lessons learnt and recommendations

This chapter offers a summary of lessons learnt and provides recommendations for future projects on CE including capacity building dimensions.

No one size fits all

Equipping the diversity of city stakeholders with circular skills is not a straightforward process. First, we acknowledge that a city transition needs to happen at various levels with different stakeholders requiring specific knowledge and skills to be able to engage in a transition. At citizen level, there is a need to build the case for circular consumption. This new paradigm forces citizens to rethink the mainstream pattern of production and consumption where a take-make-waste linear approach prevails. Nudging citizen behaviour into a circular mindset where consumption patterns are challenged, where products are to be taken care of, used for longer, repaired, shared and eventually recycled, takes time and efforts. City representatives on the other hand, beyond selling the benefits of circularity, need to concretely understand how circular principles and levers can be integrated into existing practices, often rooted in a siloed approach. SMEs and businesses in general need inspiring examples of circular business practices providing clear benefits as well as concrete how-to guidance. The diversity of profiles associated with the circular transition therefore requires different skills and knowledge that is complex to implement in a generalised way. Tailored approaches need to be developed based on the need and the level of requirements of each individual stakeholders' group.

Second, cities in Europe operate in various cultural contexts, with a different level of awareness on the topic, and different degrees of implementation. For some cities, the need to change is widely understood, emerging regenerative practices are multiplying, and the focus is turning towards multi-levels governance processes to scale up the transition. For other cities however, systemic structures are still rooted in the old paradigm and the level of awareness around circularity is still in its infancy. The content of training resources therefore needs to be contextualised in order to be fully effective.

Online content fatigue

The Covid-19 pandemic occurring in the middle of the project has disrupted traditional approaches to capacity building. The impossibility to hold physical trainings and workshops created a massive shift where online meetings, workshops and trainings became the new normal. If on one hand, this disruption created opportunities to attend an exponential offer of online training events, on the other hand, the multiplication of web events focusing on "circular everything" made it rather challenging to attract and capture an audience willing to take the time to learn and digest new knowledge between two other online

meetings. At the end of the project, a certain online fatigue is occurring, creating additional difficulties in designing attractive capacity building content.

Learn global, act local

The REFLOW Academy has thus tried to navigate between the complexity and diversity of topics to cover to make a city circular, adopting a portfolio of resources based on different learning pathways, from a short podcast to listen to when commuting, a lunch webinar break filled with straight to the point interventions, to a lengthier set of elearning courses, taking the necessary time to reflect on the different lenses that make cities circular. The limits of this online global strategy though are reflected in the impossibility to concretely take a more hands-on approach in which close physical interactions with learners, through coaching, mentoring and co-learning practices make it possible to go from knowledge acquisition to concrete knowledge implementation. A blended learning approach taking the most of online global capacity building resources but leaving space for decentralized physical interactive learning should therefore be recommended for further developments.

10 Annexes

ANNEX 1: REFLOW ACADEMY ECOURSES EVALUATION

The following document provides an overview of the beta-testing evaluation. For the purpose of the beta-testing, 12 individuals were asked to register to the learning platform and go through the three courses.

In the first section, profile, age, qualifications, and CE experience are outlined. In section 2, the content and architecture of the platform are assessed.

1. PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

1.1 AGE PROFILE

When asked about their profile, the majority of beta-testers identified as between the ages of 23-32 while thirty-three percent reported as between the ages of 33-42 years old.

1.2 JOB PROFILE

The majority reported as being employed or self-employed (41.7%), while 25% identify themselves as managers, and the rest are equally split between student, consultant, researcher/professor, and public authority/civil servant.

1.3 EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

The majority of beta-testers had an educational background in legal, economic, and social sciences.

1.4 PREVIOUS CE LEARNING EXPERIENCE

The majority of beta-testers chose to test "Introduction to the Circular Economy," which could be because the majority also stated that they have never before participated in a course on the Circular Economy.

2. RESULTS OF THE EVALUATION

Testers were asked several questions regarding the content and structure of the courses and were asked to rate the statements based on a 1-5 scale with 1 being strongly disagree and 5 being strongly agree.

2.1 CONTENT EVALUATION

When asked about the content, the majority agreed that the content was interesting and informative and well-structured. Beta-testers were also asked to use the same scale to rank how well the material corresponds to the course objectives. The results were overwhelming agreement with the course corresponding to the learning objectives and covering the topic of interest.

Content Value: The material provided corresponds to the learning objectives.

12 responses

The course is complete and covers the topic of interest.

12 responses

The content was interesting and informative.

12 responses

Structure of content: the content is well-structured.

12 responses

2.2 LEARNING EXPERIENCE

Visuals

Visuals and multi-media materials break up the text and help the learner to understand the material.

12 responses

Illustrations

The quality of the illustration and video is good and effectively supports the content.

12 responses

Adaptation to own life

Materials are designed so that learners can apply the gained knowledge to their own lives.

12 responses

Quiz and assessment

The assessments (quizzes/tests) are clear, useful, and correspond to the learning material.

12 responses

Platform navigation

It is easy to understand where I am within the e-learning platform architecture.

12 responses

2.3 EXPECTATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The REFLOW training course met my expectations.

12 responses

To end the survey, beta-testers were asked if they would recommend the REFLOW Academy to others and all responded with, "Yes."

12 responses

3. CHANGES TO THE FINAL ELEARNING PLATFORM

Based on the results of the survey of beta-testers' experiences, the e-Learning team outlined possible changes and improvements to the platform. Beta-testers' suggestions were divided into four categories:

1. **Yes to change** - where the suggested change was both possible and desirable
2. **Not relevant** - where the suggestion was not relevant. For example, the user requesting a change based on their failure to press the "Done" button after finishing a lesson.
3. **Not in the scope of the project** - where the suggestion did not fit within the scope of the REFLOW project. For example, asking for more information on methods of recycling which is not a part of circular business model innovation.
4. **Not technically possible** - where the suggestion is not possible within the technical confines of the LearnDash LMS system. For example, changing the navigation bar.

All suggested changes that fell under, "Yes to change," were then altered within the platform.

Key changes are summarized below:

Content

- Integration of additional REFLOW content related to pilots in course 1
- Link with additional CE tools in courses 2 and 3.
- Reframing of conversation scenario formulation into question prompts.

Technical

- Preparation of a navigation guide to facilitate users in using the platform

- Fixing issues related to flip boxes in course 1
- Fixing of links (new tabs)
- Fixing of technical issues

